

POLLUTION AND HUMAN HEALTH

P.S. Nargesh

Govt College Dharampuri Distt. Dhar (M.P.)

ABSTRACT

There are Literally Thousands of sources of these gases. Scientific evidence indicates that ground level – ozone not only affects people with impaired respiratory systems, but healthy adults and children as well. Nature and sources of the pollutant effects on human health and the environment. Increased combustion of fossil fuels in the last century is responsible for the progressive change in the atmospheric composition. Air pollutants, such as carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), ozone (O₃), heavy metals, and respirable particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), differ in their chemical composition, reaction properties, emission, time of disintegration and ability to diffuse in long or short distances. Air pollution has both acute and chronic effects on human health, affecting a number of different systems and organs. It ranges from minor upper respiratory irritation to chronic respiratory and heart disease, lung cancer, acute respiratory infections in children and chronic bronchitis in adults, aggravating pre-existing heart and lung disease, or asthmatic attacks. These effects of air pollutants on human health and their mechanism of action are briefly discussed.

Keywords:

Air pollutant, Human health, ozone, health and effects, nature/Emissions.

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Sources of the Pollutant Ground-level ozone (the primary constituent of smog) is the most complex, difficult to control, and pervasive of the six principal pollutants. Unlike other pollutants, ozone is not emitted directly into the air by specific sources. Ozone is created by sunlight acting on nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions in the air. There are literally thousands of sources of these gases. Some of the more common sources include gasoline vapors, chemical solvents, combustion products of various fuels, and consumer products. They can originate from large industrial facilities, gas stations, and small businesses such as bakeries and dry cleaners. Often these "precursor" gases are emitted in one area, but the actual chemical reactions, stimulated by sunlight and temperature, take place in another. Combined emissions from motor vehicles and stationary sources can be carried hundreds of miles from their origins, forming high ozone concentrations over very large regions.

HEALTH AND OTHER EFFECTS

Scientific evidence indicates that ground-level ozone not only affects people with impaired respiratory systems but healthy adults and children as well. Exposure to ozone for 6 to 7 hours, even at relatively low concentrations, significantly reduces lung function and induces respiratory

inflammation in normal, healthy people during periods of moderate exercise. It can be accompanied by symptoms such as chest pain, coughing, nausea, and pulmonary congestion. Recent studies provide evidence of an association between elevated ozone levels and increases in hospital admissions for respiratory problems in several U.S. cities. Results from animal studies indicate that repeated exposure to high levels of ozone for several months or more can produce permanent structural damage in the lungs. EPA's health-based national air quality standard for ozone is 0.12 ppm (measured at the highest hour during the day). Ozone is also responsible for several billion dollars of agricultural crop yield loss in the U.S. each year.

NITROGEN DIOXIDE (NO₂)

NATURE AND SOURCES OF THE POLLUTANT

Nitrogen dioxide belongs to a family of highly reactive gases called nitrogen oxides (NO_x). These gases form when fuel is burned at high temperatures, and come principally from motor vehicle exhaust and stationary sources such as electric utilities and industrial boilers. A suffocating, brownish gas, nitrogen dioxide is a strong oxidizing agent that reacts in the air to form corrosive nitric acid, as well as toxic organic nitrates. It also plays a major role in the atmospheric reactions that produce ground-

HEALTH AND OTHER EFFECTS

Nitrogen dioxide can irritate the lungs and lower resistance to respiratory infections such as influenza. The effects of short-term exposure are still unclear, but continued or frequent exposure to concentrations that are typically much higher than those normally found in the ambient air may cause increased incidence of acute respiratory illness in children. EPA's health-based national air quality standard for NO₂ is 0.053 ppm (measured as an annual average). Nitrogen oxides are important in forming ozone and may affect both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Nitrogen oxides in the air are a potentially significant contributor to a number of environmental effects such as acid rain and eutrophication in coastal waters like the Chesapeake Bay. Eutrophication occurs when a body of water suffers an increase in nutrients that reduce the amount of oxygen in the water, producing an environment that is destructive to fish and other animal life.

NATURE AND SOURCES OF THE POLLUTANTS

Particulate matter is the term for solid or liquid particles found in the air. Some particles are large or dark enough to be seen as soot or smoke. Others are so small they can be detected only with an electron microscope. Because particles originate from a variety of mobile and stationary sources (diesel trucks, wood stoves, power plants, etc.), their chemical and physical compositions vary widely.

HEALTH AND OTHER EFFECTS

In 1987, EPA replaced the earlier Total Suspended Particulate (TSP) air quality standard with a PM-10 standard. The standard focuses on smaller particles that are likely responsible for adverse health effects because of their ability to reach the lower regions of the respiratory tract. The PM-10 standard includes particles with a diameter of 10 micrometers or less (0.0004 inches or one-seventh the width of a human hair). EPA's health-based national air quality standard for PM-10 is 50 micrograms per cubic meter (measured as an annual average) and 150 micrograms per cubic

meter (measured as a daily average). In 1997, EPA promulgated a PM-2.5 standard which includes particles with a diameter of 2.5 microns or less.

Major concerns for human health from exposure to particulate matter are: effects on breathing and respiratory systems, damage to lung tissue, cancer, and premature death. The elderly, children, and people with chronic lung disease, influenza, or asthma, tend to be especially sensitive to the effects of particulate matter. Acidic particulate matter can also damage manmade materials and is a major cause of reduced visibility in many parts of the U.S. for more information on the health effects of particulate matter.

NATURE AND SOURCES OF THE POLLUTANT

Sulfur dioxide belongs to the family of sulfur oxide gases (SO_x). These gases are formed when fuel containing sulfur (mainly coal and oil) is burned, and during metal smelting and other industrial-processes.

The major health concerns associated with exposure to high concentrations of SO₂ include effects on breathing, respiratory illness, alterations in pulmonary defenses, and aggravation of existing cardiovascular disease. Major subgroups of the population that are most sensitive to SO₂ include asthmatics and individuals with cardiovascular disease or chronic lung disease (such as bronchitis or emphysema) as well as children and the elderly. EPA's health-based national air quality standard for SO₂ is 0.03 ppm (measured on an annual average) and 0.14 ppm (measured over 24 hours). Emissions of SO₂ also can damage the foliage of trees and agricultural crops.

HEALTH EFFECTS

Exposure to lead mainly occurs through inhalation of air and ingestion of lead in food, paint, water, soil, or dust. Lead accumulates in the body in blood, bone, and soft tissue. Because it is not readily excreted, lead can also affect the kidneys, liver, nervous system, and other organs. Excessive exposure to lead may cause anemia, kidney disease, reproductive disorders, and neurological impairments such as seizures, mental retardation, and/or behavioral disorders. Even at low doses, lead exposure is associated with changes in fundamental enzymatic, energy transfer, and other processes in the body. Fetuses and children are especially susceptible to low doses of lead, often suffering central nervous system damage or slowed growth. Recent studies show that lead may be a factor in high blood pressure and subsequent heart disease in middle-aged white males. Lead may also contribute to osteoporosis in postmenopausal women.

CARBON MONOXIDE (CO)

NATURE AND SOURCES OF THE POLLUTANT

Carbon monoxide is a colorless odorless poisonous gas formed when carbon in fuels is not burned completely. It is a byproduct of motor vehicle exhaust, which contributes more than two-thirds of all CO emissions nationwide. In cities, automobile exhaust can cause as much as 95 percent of all CO emissions. These emissions can result in high concentrations of CO, particularly in local areas with heavy traffic

HEALTH AND OTHER EFFECTS

Carbon monoxide enters the bloodstream and reduces oxygen delivery to the body's organs and tissues. The health threat from CO is most serious for those who suffer from cardiovascular disease. Healthy individuals are also affected, but only at higher levels of exposure. Exposure to

elevated CO levels is associated with visual impairment, reduced work capacity, and reduced manual dexterity, poor learning ability, and difficulty in performing complex tasks. EPA's health based national air quality standard for CO is 9 parts per million (ppm) [measured over 8 hours].

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